

Durance River modelling for environment and safety management

Viard Thomas
Hydraulic Engineering Center
EDF
La Motte Servolex, France
Thomas.viard@edf.fr

Duclercq Marion
Hydraulic Engineering Center
EDF
La Motte Servolex, France

Abstract— Durance River in South East of France is highly influenced by Serre-Ponçon and Sainte Croix dams. With those dams, regular floods no longer clear vegetation in Durance River bed. EDF manages those dams and has to clear vegetation to replace flood action to avoid worsening extreme floods. Authorities in charge of flood safety management ask EDF for an important clearing of vegetation, and authorities in charge of Environment ask EDF to preserve vegetation as much as possible. To reconcile those two opposite objectives, a prefectural decree was published asking EDF to preserve vegetation if it doesn't worsen water level in flood plain (increase between with and without vegetation of less than 5 cm in highly sensitive areas – urban areas – and less than 10 cm in moderately sensitive areas – agricultural areas). To answer that prefectural decree, EDF chooses to model Durance River from Serre-Ponçon dam to its confluence with Rhone River (204 km). 14 TELEMAC-2D models are or will be built to optimise the clearing of vegetation. Durance bed changes often, therefore those models and their calibration are updated regularly.

This article focuses on two models: “Bonpas Le Rhône”, just upstream of the confluence with the Rhône River, and “Brillanne”, a part of Durance between the confluence with the Bléone River and the confluence with the Verdon River. It details methodology for construction, updates, calibration and way of optimisation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Construction of the Serre-Ponçon dam and Sainte Croix dam significantly modified flows downstream in the Durance River. EDF, as a manager of those dams, have to limit growth of vegetation in river bed to avoid increase of damages in flood plain in case of significant flood (until 100-year return flood).

On the other hand, vegetation in river bed represents a real environmental interest for fauna and flora (beavers, many kind of birds...).

Therefore Authorities ask EDF to reconcile two opposite objectives:

- To maintain a good level of safety against floods
- To limit environmental impact of vegetation clearing

Authorities published a prefectural decree asking EDF to model Durance River with and without bed vegetation to compare free surface elevation. That decree defines the following criterion: “An interesting environmental site can be preserved from vegetation clearing if the averaged increase of free surface

elevation is limited to 5 cm in highly sensitive areas and to 10 cm in moderately sensitive areas”.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Vocabulary

The part of river bed where EDF has to limit growth of vegetation is called the “clearing” channel. The width of this clearing channel is defined by law since 1979. Its width varies from 60 m downstream Serre-Ponçon dam to 400 m just upstream confluence with Rhone River (Fig. 1). Exact localisation of this clearing channel is not defined by law, but it is supposed to be centred on the river axis, except locally (if a river bank is significantly higher than the other, clearing channel is deported on the lowest bank).

To evaluate the increase of free surface elevation, the reference case is a clearing channel without vegetation. It is called the reference channel.

The objective of EDF is to keep the maximum of interesting environmental sites while respecting the prefectural decree. The final channel, which is reaching EDF objectives, is called “optimised” channel.

Area	Surface	Length	Width
HD01	48 ha	11 km	60 m
HD02	45 ha	12 km	60 m
HD03	117 ha	14 km	100 m
HD04	87 ha	10,5 km	100 m
HD05	83 ha	12,5 km	100 m
MD01	45 ha	5,5 km	100 m
MD02	107 ha	7 km	200 m
MD03	137 ha	7 km	200 m
MD04	188 ha	9,5 km	200 m
MD05	141 ha	6,5 km	250 m
MD06	150 ha	6 km	250 m
MD07	89 ha	3,7 km	250 m
MD08	188 ha	7,5 km	250 m
BD01	172 ha	8 km	250 m
BD02	195 ha	8,5 km	250 m
BD03	58 ha	2,8 km	250 m
BD04	92 ha	4 km	250 m
BD05	282 ha	11,7 km	250 m
BD06	453 ha	15 km	350 m
BD07	414 ha	14,3 km	300 m
BD08	116 ha	4,3 km	300 m
BD09	396 ha	11,4 km	400 m
BD10	443 ha	11,2 km	400 m

Figure 1: Width of the clearing channel along Durance River (the ‘REF’ of each sector is indicated on the above map)

B. Model construction

14 TELEMAC-2D models are or will be built to optimise the clearing channel.

1) *Bathymetry/topography*: In 2016, a LIDAR was done for all the river bed topography from Serre-Ponçon dam to Rhone River (204 km) during low-water periods. For bathymetry, cross sections were also measured every 500m. During low water periods, water depths are in general less than 20 cm in Durance River, therefore LIDAR is main source used to build the River bed geometry of the TELEMAC model; cross section are used only for pools. Local bathymetry were done for dam reservoirs. For Flood plain topography, a LIDAR from French National Geographic Institute (IGN) is used. Finally, local topography information (from Syndicat Mixte d’Aménagement de la vallée de la Durance – SMAVD – organization in charge of flood mitigation on Durance River) is used to model flood protection structures.

2) *Mesh*: the average mesh size is 10 m in river bed, without constraint lines for easy update in the future. ; it is between 20 and 30 m in flood plain, except for flood protection structures. Thoses structures are modelled with 5 constraint lines (2 at the bottom, 3 at the crest) to avoid ‘numerical overtopping’ (Fig. 2). The mesh size for the structures depends on their type : 10 m for weirs and bridges, 20 m for dykes, 40 m for roads and railways.

Figure 2: mesh for flood protection structures

3) *Boundary conditions*: hydrographs are imposed upstream. The shape of 1994 main flood is reused with homothety for maximal discharge. Rating curves are used downstream. Floods of return periods ranging between 30 and 100 year are studied.

4) *Strickler coefficient*: during model construction, the following Strickler coefficients are used:

- Reservoirs, lakes, pools : $35 \text{ m}^{1/3}/\text{s}$
- River bed: $30 \text{ m}^{1/3}/\text{s}$
- Fields, dykes and rockfill weirs: $20 \text{ m}^{1/3}/\text{s}$
- Vegetation with low density: $15 \text{ m}^{1/3}/\text{s}$
- Urban areas: $10 \text{ m}^{1/3}/\text{s}$
- Vegetation with high density: $8 \text{ m}^{1/3}/\text{s}$

C. Model validation

To optimise the clearing channel, vegetated areas and cleared areas are modelled with different Strickler coefficients. Therefore the usual step of calibration of the model must rather be considered here as a validation step, since Strickler coefficients are changed for each simulation.

Models are validated jointly between EDF and SMAVD. SMAVD has a large experience of Durance River that helps EDF to interpret model results. Floods marks are completed with information from flood witnesses about specific flooded areas.

Air photographs were done simultaneously with the LIDAR done in March 2016 used for the bathymetry. Those photos are used to define the state of vegetation in clearing channel for validation step.

A significant flood ($1650 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$) occurred in November 2016 downstream to the confluence between Durance and Buech River. For models downstream to this confluence, that flood is used for validation. For models upstream to that confluence, only one flood occurred in the last 20 years. It was in 2008. Between 2008 and 2016 bathymetry and vegetation of Durance river bed have changed. Thus, validation is more complicated because of those evolutions.

D. Data for Model using

1) *Sensitive areas*: The prefectural decree gives criteria for sensitive areas (an averaged increase of 5 cm in highly sensitive and 10 cm in moderately sensitive areas). But that decree does not clearly define the sensitive areas nor the surface areas to average free surface elevation. Therefore, first step was to ask authorities for the definition of sensitive areas. Highly sensitive areas are urban areas (defined in flooding prevention maps or in Corine Land Cover [1] data base if flooding prevention maps does not exist). Moderately sensitive areas are agricultural areas, except meadows (surface areas are defined with Corine Land Cover data base).

2) *Environmental stakes*: before using a model, environmental inventory are done to localize vegetation with high environmental interests in the clearing channel. The optimised channel will try to take into account this inventory. Vegetation with low environmental interests (invasive plants...) will be cleared first.

3) *Studied floods*: Prefectural decree gives criteria regarding the increase of the free surface elevation “for the moderately sensitive areas overflowing flood, for the high sensitive areas overflowing flood and for dykes design flood”. In a model, there are a lot of sensitive areas and often a lot of dykes. Therefore, those 3 floods cannot be exactly defined. EDF chose to design the optimised channel on one flood – 30, 50 or 100 year return period – and then to validate that optimised channel with many floods with a return period ranging between 30 and 100 year (with a step of 100 m³/s).

E. Model using

From the validated model, the sensitive areas map and the environmental stakes, the final channel to be cleared can be optimised. This is usually done in 2 steps: one “manual” step to design the optimised channel with one flood and one “automatic” step to validate the optimised channel with many floods.

- *Manual step*: 30, 50 and 100 year return period floods are simulated with the refence channel (cleared channel – Strickler coefficient of 30 m^{1/3}/s). The most relevant flood is chosen for optimisation (depending on observed overflowing between river bed and flood plain and flooding kinetic). Then the chosen flood is simulated with the actual state of vegetation (Strickler coefficient of 8 m^{1/3}/s in areas with vegetation – vegetation is supposed to become mature – and 30 m^{1/3}/s in areas without vegetation – those values are based on SMAVD experience feedback). The results of that simulation are compared to the results with the reference channel. If the criteria the from prefectural decree are met, channels with more vegetated zones are tested. On the contrary, if the criteria are not met, channels with less vegetated zones are tested following these principles :

- trying to keep vegetation upstream of highly sensitive areas to limit flooding downstream and where there are interesting environmental sites

- Vegetation is cleared downstream of highly sensitive areas and near connections between river bed and flood plain to lower water levels at those key points.

Figure 3: Bonpas Le Rhône model – sensitive areas map (highly sensitive in red and moderately sensitive in yellow)

Ultimately, vegetation is maximised with respect of the decree.

- *Automatic step:* Once an optimised channel is found for the chosen flood, this channel has to be validated for other floods. All floods with a return period ranging between 30 and 100 year with a step of 100 m³/s are simulated twice: with the optimised channel and with the reference channel. For each flood, the maximal water level with the optimised channel is compared to the water level with the reference channel. An averaged difference is computed in each sensitive area to validate the optimised channel for each flood. Few adjustments of the optimised channel can be necessary to meet the decree criteria for all floods.

III. BONPAS LE RHÔNE MODEL

This methodology was first applied to define the optimised channel in the downstream part of Durance River. Model was built from Bonpas Dam to Rhône confluence (BD10 in Fig. 1). As Fig. 3 shows, floods mainly concern the left bank of Durance River and this bank is almost everywhere covered by sensitive areas.

The first simulations with a Strickler coefficient of 8 m^{1/3}/s where vegetation is not cleared showed that no mature vegetation could be preserved to respect the criteria of the prefectural decree. Therefore, it was chosen to partially clear vegetation to find a compromise between total clearing and mature vegetation. The Strickler coefficient corresponding to partially cleared vegetation was calculated with Baptist formula [2]:

$$K = \frac{C_k}{R_h^{1/6}} \quad C_k = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\frac{1}{C_b^2} + \frac{C_d m D H}{2g}}}$$

With H water depth, C_k Chézy coefficient, C_b Chézy coefficient of a cleared area, C_d drag coefficient, m vegetation density, D averaged diameter of trees, and R_h hydraulic radius. A Strickler coefficient of 19 m^{1/3}/s was associated to partially cleared vegetation. With that coefficient, few interesting environmental sites could be kept.

After many simulations of the 100 year return period flood (5 000 m³/s), an optimised channel was found. The flood discharge for 30 year return period is 3 000 m³/s. Therefore 42 simulations, 21 simulations by 100 m³/s step for the optimised channel and as many simulations for the reference channel, were necessary to validate the final optimised channel (Fig. 4).

Figure 4: optimised channel for Bonpas Le Rhône model (red and orange: to clear, green and yellow: to partially clear)

IV. BRILLANNE MODEL

The Brillanne model was the second model following the methodology explained above. This model corresponds to MD04 in Fig. 1. As Fig. 5 shows, floods mainly concern the left bank of Durance River and there is a lot of space between the river bed and the sensitive areas.

The clearing channel is 200m width in this model but the active river bed is larger. Contrary to Bonpas Le Rhône model, mature vegetation will not grow in all areas where EDF does not clear. Therefore, air photographs between 2000 and 2016 (around 8 photographs are available) were used to determine the exact active bed of Durance River. Then, averaged vegetation surfaces in that bed were estimated on each photograph and analysed regarding occurred floods and past clearing done by EDF to determine a state of vegetation without EDF clearing. This state of vegetation was assimilated to a Strickler coefficient of $24 \text{ m}^{1/3}/\text{s}$ (with few simulations).

To optimise the clearing channel in Brillanne model, a Strickler coefficient of $24 \text{ m}^{1/3}/\text{s}$ was used for the active river bed outside the clearing channel and for the non-cleared areas in the clearing channel.

Contrary to Bonpas Le Rhône model, thanks to floods naturally clearing vegetation in the active bed and because of less sensitive areas, many parts of the clearing channel can be preserved in the optimised channel.

The reference and the optimised channels are compared considering an averaged state of vegetation in the river bed outside the clearing channel. The real state of vegetation depends on recent floods. Therefore recent Air photographs are analysed before clearing works to evaluate the state of vegetation all over the river bed and to determine how to fit the optimised modelled channel.

Figure 5: Brillanne model – sensitive areas map (highly sensitive in red and moderately sensitive in yellow)

Figure 6: optimised channel for Brillanne model (orange: to clear)

V. CONCLUSION

Since building of Serre-Ponçon and Sainte Croix dams in Durance river basin, EDF has to clear vegetation in the river bed to replace the natural effect of floods on vegetation. A prefectural decree was published to reconcile safety and

environmental management during clearing works. TELEMAC modelling is done by EDF to find an optimised clearing channel respecting that prefectural decree. The methodology was established with SMAVD and Authorities. This methodology was already successfully used for 2 models with few adjustment to local context.

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REFERENCES

- [1] <https://www.data.gouv.fr/fr/datasets/corine-land-cover-occupation-des-sols-en-france/>
- [2] Baptist, M., V. Babovic, J. Rodríguez Uthurburu, M. Keijzer, R. Uittenbogaard, A. Mynett, and A. Verwey (2007), "On inducing equations for vegetation resistance", *Journal of Hydraulic Research*, 45(4), 435-450.

